

Can We Get Away with Point Kinetics? A Comparison Between Spatial Dynamics and Point Kinetics Analyses of a ULOHS in a Heat Pipe-Cooled Microreactor

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ABSTRACT

Heat pipe-cooled microreactors (HPMRs) are gaining attention as a next-generation nuclear technology for remote and distributed energy applications, offering compactness, scalability, and a high level of passive safety. Because of their small core dimensions and the relatively long neutron mean free path, resulting from the common use of graphite moderators, it is often assumed that point kinetics equations (PKEs) can adequately capture their transient behavior. However, this assumption has not been rigorously tested against spatially resolved models. This work presents a detailed comparison between point kinetics and full spatial dynamics simulations using the Discontinuous Finite Element Method with discrete ordinates (DFEM-S_n) for a representative transient in HPMRs. In particular, we analyze an idealized Unprotected Loss of Heat Sink (ULOHS) event, characterized by a relatively mild and spatially uniform power response. The results demonstrate that, even under such “gentle” conditions, PKE fails to reproduce the reference transient solution due to spectral shifts of the neutron flux shape. More importantly, the PKEs underestimate both average and peak fuel temperatures, which may lead to non-conservative safety conclusions. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first quantitative comparison between point kinetics and spatial dynamics for a microreactor, complemented by a detailed flux shape deviation analysis. These findings underscore the need for validating reduced-order models (ROMs) and integrating conservative assumptions when modeling microreactor transients for design and safety evaluation.

Keywords: Microreactor, Transient, OpenMC, Griffin, TRISO

1. INTRODUCTION

Several new reactor designs have been proposed to meet the growing energy needs driven by AI adoption and widespread electrification, including HPMRs. The use of heat pipes permits HPMRs to achieve inherently passive heat removal, while high operating temperatures lead to higher thermodynamic efficiency and potential for electricity and heat cogeneration [1, 2, 3]. With compact geometries and prevalent use of graphite as a moderator for high-temperature microreactors, point kinetics models have commonly been employed as the primary tool for simulating HPMRs, and general microreactor transients, while spatial dynamics have been applied only for asymmetric scenarios or research purposes [4, 5]. Although the PKEs demonstrated good agreement with spatial dynamics results for other advanced reactor designs, such as molten salt reactors [6], little work has been done validating the accuracy of the PKE calculations applied to thermal and epithermal HPMR transients.

In this study, we investigate the accuracy of the PKE model against a DFEM-S_n reference using the Griffin deterministic neutronics code [7] within the Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) [8]. This is accomplished by analyzing the dynamic response of an HPMR subject to an idealized ULOHS accident for the realistic HPMR (rHPMR) numerical problem [9]. Despite enforcing consistency between DFEM-S_n and PKE, the latter under-predicts the total power and average temperature throughout the transient due to the flux variation in the energy space. The under-prediction in

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power and temperature demonstrates that PKE does not guarantee accuracy or conservatism even for a quasi-spatially uniform transient like this idealized ULOHS. A neutron flux shape analysis further highlights the limitations of PKE in capturing the spatial and spectral effects resolved by the discrete ordinates solver. This analysis provides a new quantification of the applicability of PKE with respect to spatial accuracy. To the best knowledge of the authors, this is the first time the PKE model is quantitatively compared against transport-based spatial dynamics' results for microreactors.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces DFEM-S_n, the PKEs, and the flux shape analysis methodology. Emphasis is placed on how consistency was enforced. Section 3 contains an overview of the computational models and workflow, with results from the PKEs and DFEM-S_n presented in Section 4, highlighting the differences in transient behavior and neutron flux evolution across fast and thermal energy groups. Finally, Section 5 contains conclusions and draws directions for future work.

2. THEORY

2.1. Discrete Ordinates Method

Within the multigroup discrete ordinate method, the angular flux and delayed neutron precursor concentrations are determined for a set of discrete energy bins and along a finite set of directions according to the following equations:

$$\frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\partial \psi_g^n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \hat{\Omega}^n \psi_g^n + \Sigma_{t,g} \psi_g^n = \sum_{g'}^G \sum_{\ell}^L \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}^{\ell} \sum_{m=-\ell}^{\ell} \psi_{g'}^{\ell,m} R^{\ell,m}(\hat{\Omega}^n) + \frac{\chi_g^{(p)}}{4\pi} \sum_{g'}^G (1 - \beta) v \Sigma_{f,g'} \sum_{n'}^N w^{n'} \psi_{g'}^{n'} + \sum_i \frac{\chi_g^{(d,i)} \lambda_i}{4\pi} C_i. \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} = \sum_{g'}^G \beta_i v \Sigma_{f,g'} \sum_{n'}^N w^{n'} \psi_{g'}^{n'} - \lambda_i C_i. \quad (2)$$

Discretizing Equations (1) and (2) in space with the discontinuous finite element method results in the DFEM-S_n model.

2.2. Point Kinetics Method

The PKEs assume the separability of the angular flux into the product of an amplitude function and a shape function according to Equation (3):

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}, t) = P(t) \Psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}). \quad (3)$$

The time-evolution of $P(t)$ is described by the PKE model [10]:

$$\frac{dP(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho(t) - \beta}{\Lambda} P(t) + \sum_i \lambda_i C_i(t), \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dC_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{\beta_i}{\Lambda} P(t) - \lambda_i C_i(t). \quad (5)$$

Consistency is enforced between DFEM-S_n and PKE models by obtaining the effective PK parameters, β , β_i , and Λ , from DFEM-S_n in lieu of OpenMC [11, 12]. We performed forward and adjoint DFEM-S_n eigenvalue calculations to obtain the forward and adjoint angular flux, respectively. From the latter, the PK parameters are computed with bilinear products according to their definition [10]. Additionally, dynamic reactivity is approximated by the static reactivity from the DFEM-S_n eigenvalue calculations. More details are provided in Section 3.

2.3. A Metric to Quantify Flux Shape Variation

The PKE model is ensured to be accurate if the flux shape in the phase space, $(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega})$, is constant with respect to time. To quantify the deviation from this ideal scenario, the amplitude-normalized, group-wise scalar neutron flux was compared to the initial flux shape for each time step and at each point in space to obtain the relative shape deviation, $\Delta\hat{\phi}_g$, the average shape difference, μ_g , and the flux deviation, σ_g . The change of the deviation over time was calculated to estimate the first-order truncation of the PKE error growth using scaling constants and without requiring the PKE results:

$$\Delta\hat{\phi}_g(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\hat{\phi}_g(\mathbf{r}, t) - \hat{\phi}_g(\mathbf{r}, 0)}{\frac{1}{V} \int_V d^3r \hat{\phi}_g(\mathbf{r}, 0)} \quad (6)$$

$$\mu_g(t) = \frac{\int_V d^3r \Delta\hat{\phi}_g(\mathbf{r}, t)}{V} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_g(t) = \sqrt{\frac{\int_V d^3r [\Delta\hat{\phi}_g(\mathbf{r}, t) - \mu_g(t)]^2}{V}} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Error} \approx C_1 \sum_g \sigma_g(t) + C_2 \sum_g \frac{\partial \sigma_g}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

The metric was created to remove the transient amplitude and isolate flux shape changes. By subtracting off the mean flux shape for a given timestep, the localized deviation is obtained. The deviation's second central moment emphasizes regions of greater variation. For perfect application of point kinetics, $\Delta\hat{\phi}_g$ should match μ_g everywhere, resulting in a deviation of 0. This simple metric has inherent limitations since it cannot capture changes in the angular sub-space, and the spatial averaging equally weights all regions of the reactor. However, using the group-wise scalar flux enables us to capture not only the flux shape change in the physical space, but also in the energy space. This metric was defined based on an error estimation of the PKEs from the exact phase-space collapsed neutron transport equation. At the moment, the scaling coefficients are determined by regression fitting to the PKE error solely for demonstration purposes. An upcoming journal publication will address the detailed analytical derivation of the error.

3. CODES AND NUMERICAL MODELING

3.1. Idealized ULOHS Transient for the rHPMR

The rHPMR benchmark is designed to mimic characteristics common to HPMR designs without releasing proprietary information. Using a graphite monolithic structure, the rHPMR is a 5 MW_{th} design surrounded by a beryllium reflector and 12 control drums. In the monolith, assemblies are arrangements of TRistructural ISotropic (TRISO) particle fuel compacts and molten sodium heat pipes. For simulation purposes, heat transfer through heat pipes is modeled with a global Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC) and sink temperature. The core geometry is shown in Figure 1. The mesh used for DFEM-S_n and conduction is identical to the original model [9]. An idealized ULOHS transient was selected for this analysis due to the spatially-homogeneous change in thermal conditions during the accident scenario. In this transient, the HTCs are reduced throughout the whole reactor to simulate a total heat pipe failure. Since the HTC reduction is uniform throughout the core, the neutron flux shape profile responds as uniformly as possible for a realistic transient. The HTC evolution is presented in Table I. If the PKEs fails to replicate higher-order results with this type of transient, then it will likely produce worse discrepancies with more complex transient scenarios. All thermodynamic material properties were held constant throughout the transient.

Figure 1. OpenMC-generated (a) radial and (b) axial views of the rHPMR benchmark.

Table I. HTC values to simulate a ULOHS transient.

Time (s)	Event	HTC (W/m ² K)
0 - 10	Null transient	372
10 - 20	Linear reduction	372 → 40
20 - 15,000	No change in input	40

3.2. Transient Multiphysics Coupling for DFEM-S_n

To use DFEM-S_n with Griffin, a multi-group cross section library was first constructed using OpenMC. Cross sections were tallied using an 11-group energy structure found in the benchmark specification [9] with P₃ anisotropy. Cross sections were obtained for the operational range of temperatures from 700 K to 1400 K in 100 K isothermal increments. All simulations were performed with 500 total batches, 50 inactive batches, and 100,000 particles per batch using ENDF/B-VIII.0.

The drums were rotated to 97° to match a realistic operating configuration near criticality. Eigenvalue and ULOHS simulations are performed using 3 polar and 6 azimuthal angle discretizations. After solving the neutronics for a single timestep, the power density from the fission rate is sent to a conduction calculation in MOOSE. MOOSE then returns the material temperatures to Griffin, which adjusts the cross sections from the library to account for thermal effects. This process is repeated until converging for this timestep before moving to the next timestep in a Picard iteration scheme for a full transient.

3.3. Transient Multiphysics Coupling for PKE

For using PKEs with Griffin, an equivalent coupling scheme to DFEM-S_n is used. We perform forward and adjoint eigenvalue calculations with DFEM-S_n to provide the kinetics parameters presented in Table II. Although Equations (4) and (5) involve time-dependent kinetics parameters, they were assumed to be constant throughout the transients since changes in the adjoint and forward flux shapes are small with the ULOHS. Instead of calculating the power density, the PKE solution scales steady-state power from DFEM-S_n. Conduction is performed in MOOSE with the scaled power density, and average material temperatures are returned to the PKEs for evaluating reactivity. Figure 2 shows the iteration schemes for PKEs and DFEM-S_n. To incorporate temperature feedback, two reactivity models were applied using the average fuel, monolith, and reflector temperatures: direct multilinear interpolation of temperature state points using the Quickhull algorithm [13] and barycentric interpolation, and a linear reactivity model with averaged reactivity coefficients shown in Equation (10). The DFEM-S_n eigenvalue calculations provided the state points at isothermal material temperatures with increments of 100 K. Smaller increments were tested, but provided no noticeable improvement in the final results.

Table II. Kinetics parameters used in the PKE model.

Parameter	Λ (μ s)	λ_1 (1/s)	λ_2 (1/s)	λ_3 (1/s)	λ_4 (1/s)	λ_5 (1/s)	λ_6 (1/s)
Value	164.2	0.01334	0.03274	0.12080	0.30278	0.84949	2.85300
Parameter	β	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4	β_5	β_6
Value (pcm)	669.11	23.076	119.71	114.80	258.58	107.84	45.111

$$\rho(t) [\text{pcm}] = -3.9642(T_f(t) - T_f(0)) - 1.8080(T_m(t) - T_m(0)) + 0.5943(T_r(t) - T_r(0)) \quad (10)$$

 Figure 2. Multiphysics coupling schemes for evaluating PKE against DFEM-S_n.

4. RESULTS

The PKE and DFEM-S_n models were initialized from steady-state conditions from a DFEM-S_n eigenvalue calculation coupled to the MOOSE conduction model. Figure 3 presents the power and average temperature as a function of time, while Figure 4 shows the direct reactivity-based PKE discrepancy from the results of DFEM-S_n. Initially, the monolith temperature is heated by the decreased effectiveness of the heat pipes. The decreased heat transfer raises the fuel temperature and decreases the reactivity through Doppler effects. The reflector temperature begins to increase and adds positive reactivity to counteract the fuel and monolith temperature, slightly recovering the power. In Figure 3, the PKE models substantially over-predict the negative reactivity insertion, producing a sharper power drop and lower average temperatures. The direct model provides much better agreement with DFEM-S_n compared to the standard linear reactivity model with constant reactivity coefficients. As shown in Figure 4, the maximum power difference is 23.5% between DFEM-S_n and linear, and 7.6% between DFEM-S_n and the direct method. Since the linear model is one of the most common methods for capturing temperature feedback mechanisms for ROMs, it is an interesting take-away observation that the linear reactivity model is insufficient to accurately capture the power variation even for idealized quasi-homogeneous transient scenarios.

Based on the results in Figure 4, PKE does not provide conservative results for a ULOHS. Although the temperature error remains below 1%, material averaging masks local deviations, giving a false appearance of better agreement. The under-prediction of the maximum temperature approaches 20 K towards the end of the transient. Special consideration should be taken for future deployment of reactors using

Figure 3. (a) Power and (b) average temperature transient profiles for PKE and DFEM- S_n models.

Figure 4. Error of PKE with direct reactivity feedback from DFEM- S_n in (a) power and (b) temperature over time.

Figure 5. (a) Flux shape deviation from DFEM- S_n and (b) error estimation using scaled σ_g and $\frac{\partial \sigma_g}{\partial t}$.

PKE as analysis with no guarantee of conservatism for transient behavior. Figure 5 shows the the flux deviation and an estimation of the PKE error from the flux deviation and its time derivative. While the fast flux remains largely unchanged, the thermal flux exhibits relative increases to 12.5%. Also, the total flux presents a lower deviation than individual flux groups and may lead to erroneous verification for PKE. The deviation and its rate of change offer a cursory prediction of the error growth with the scaling constants chosen to fit the PKE error and more rigorous theoretical derivation planned for the future.

5. CONCLUSIONS

HPMRs offer promising features for meeting rising energy demands, but their compact, graphite-moderated designs challenge the validity of point-kinetics models typically used for microreactor transient analysis. Using the rHPMR benchmark under an idealized ULOHS scenario, we compared full-order and PKE neutronics simulations performed with OpenMC, Griffin, and MOOSE. The results show that PKE does not reliably reproduce spatial-dynamics behavior, even for this mild transient, and the resulting discrepancies can lead to non-conservative temperature predictions. Although the transient studied here is nearly spatially homogeneous, the observed non-conservative behavior suggests that PKE limitations may be more pronounced in complex accident scenarios and in other microreactor concepts with similar neutronic characteristics. The proposed flux-shape deviation metric provides a quantitative basis for understanding these errors and will be further refined for a priori error estimation.

Despite the discrepancy with PKE, quasi-static methods may provide reasonable accuracy with similar improvements in computational efficiency. Periodically updating the flux shape will reset the flux deviation and consequently reduce PKE error. Different reduction methods and iteration schemes will be explored in the future to further support analysis, development, and deployment of HPMR technology.

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NOMENCLATURE

v_g Neutron velocity for energy group g

$\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}, t)$ Continuous energy angular flux

$\psi_g^n(\mathbf{r}, t)$ Angular flux for energy group g in the direction of $\hat{\Omega}^n$

$\psi_{g'}^{\ell, m}$ Spherical harmonic flux of degree ℓ and order m for the energy group g'

$\Sigma_{t, g}, \nu\Sigma_{f, g'}$ Total and neutron production cross sections for group g

$\Sigma_{s, g' \rightarrow g}^{\ell}$ Scattering cross section from group g' to g and spherical harmonic degree ℓ

$R^{\ell, m}(\hat{\Omega}^n)$ Paired spherical harmonics function of degree ℓ and order m

$w^{n'}$ Angular quadrature weight for direction $\hat{\Omega}^{n'}$

$\chi_g^{(p)}, \chi_g^{(d, i)}$ Prompt and i th delayed neutron emission energy spectrum

β, β_i Total and the i th precursor group delayed neutron fractions

$C_i(t), \lambda_i$ Delayed neutron precursor concentration and corresponding decay constant for the i th precursor group

$P(t)$ Flux amplitude normalized to power

- $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega})$ Flux shape
 $\rho(t)$ Dynamic reactivity
 Λ Mean neutron generation time
 $\hat{\phi}_g(\mathbf{r}, t)$ Normalized scalar flux for group g
 T_f, T_m, T_r Average fuel, monolith, and reflector temperatures
 V Reactor volume
 C_1, C_2 Scaling constants for approximating PKE error

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